

Impact of heatwave events on health of vegetation in Milton Keynes from 2016 to 2020

Ramla Khan^{*1}, Kadmiel Maseyk¹ Philip Wheeler¹, Joseph Fennell¹, Konstantin Stefanov²

¹School of Environment, Earth, and Ecosystem sciences, The Open University, Milton Keynes

²School of Physical Sciences, Open University, Milton Keynes

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Summary

Plants have several vital environmental and societal benefits, but the recurring high intensity and frequent heatwaves every year in the UK are damaging them. In this research, first the past heatwaves are detected using threshold of MetOffice of UK and Era5 satellite data of Copernicus. The damage caused to different vegetation types (woodlands, grasslands, and crops) due to the heatwaves was analysed using Sentinel-2 and normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI). An app was also generated for this research that computes the spatial maps with respect to different vegetation types. The link to the app is provided in the methodology section.

KEYWORDS: heatwaves, landcover change, Era5, Sentinel-2, google-earth-engine

1. Introduction

1.1. Heatwaves

Studies show that climate change is responsible for the rising temperature, dry summers, and increase in the frequency of extreme events (Ritchie *et al.*, 2019). Heatwaves are occurring with increasing frequency in the UK. From the 4th to the 13th of August in the year 2010, the UK suffered 2000 more deaths during a ten-day-long heatwave event. Similarly, in the year 2006, the UK suffered 680 excess deaths and 300 deaths in 2009 due to separate heatwave events (PHE, 2015).

According to the Met office of the UK, a heatwave occurs when for three or more consecutive days the maximum temperature value is above the threshold value based on the climate conditions of the area[†]. As shown in figure 1, the threshold value for the central region is 26 °C, London is 28 °C, most of the south-east parts is 27 °C, while the rest of the UK has a limit of 25 °C.

* ramlakhan@open.ac.uk

† <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/weather/learn-about/weather/types-of-weather/temperature/heatwave>

Figure 1 Threshold temperature for heatwave events in the UK

1.2. Vegetation change:

Trees and plants are adaptable to their environment. Those growing in a warmer environment or originating from a warmer climate have a higher tolerance for high temperatures as compared to the trees from the colder regions (Nievola *et al.*, 2017). The temperature range of 15°C to 30°C is optimal for the growth of most plants in a temperate climate. Temperature above 30°C for a long span induces stress and hinders the growth of many plants (Sanchez, 2021).

The warmer climate and shortage of water in the southeast region of the UK are negatively impacting the health of vegetation (Ritchie *et al.*, 2019).

Records have shown that damage due to high temperature starts happening before the heatwave event strike the area, so it becomes crucial to plan long-term (PHE, 2015), and analyse the trend in vegetation change before and after the event instead of only observing it during the event.

2. Datasets

2.1. Era5:

In this research, the daily aggregated data of climate variables released by the Copernicus climate change services are used. This data has in total seven parameters, but the one used here is: the maximum air temperature values that are observed at 2m height from the ground. The availability date range for this data is from 1979 to three months before the present date (Hersbach *et al.*, 2020).

2.2. Sentinel-2 1C:

This is a multispectral dataset with a good resolution collected over an interval of five days. The bands used in this study (red and NIR) have a spatial resolution of 10m. This data is available from June/2015 to the present date (ESA, 2015).

2.3. UKCEH LCM:

This is a landcover map generated at a resolution of 20m for the whole UK using a combination of bootstrap training and random forest classifier over seasonal images from Sentinel-2. It has in total of twenty-one landcover types (UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology, 2020).

3. Methodology

3.1. Heatwave identification

As mentioned earlier, a consecutive maximum air temperature of 27 °C or above for three days in Milton Keynes is termed a heatwave event. Using this threshold and the data of daily maximum temperature for the past 5 years (2016 to 2020) from Era5, the past heatwave events were identified.

3.2. Vegetation change with heatwaves

To observe the vegetation change and detect the presence or absence of a trend during historic

heatwaves incidents, vegetation index, normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) was computed from the 10m resolution data of Sentinel 2 using equation 1. The months where heatwaves were common occurrence were plotted against the vegetation index. Then the change in the spatial pattern of different vegetation classes like woodlands, crops, and shrubs in Milton Keynes was observed at an interval of 15 days before and after the event.

$$NDVI=(NIR-Red)/(NIR+Red) \quad (1)$$

The spatial maps were generated using the app [Vegetation Index: Normalized Difference Vegetation Index \(NDVI\)](#)

4. Results

4.1. Heatwave identification

Table 1 indicates that the date, duration and peak temperature varies between years. In the year 2016, there was only one heatwave event detected in June that lasted for three days. In the year 2017, a heatwave in June lasted for five consecutive days. The year 2018 was the worst with three heatwave events that lasted for five to six days each time. 2019 has two heatwave events that spanned for 4 and 5 days but were high in intensity.

Table 1 Heatwave events detected in Milton Keynes from 2016 to 2020

Year	Date		No. of days	Average temperature	Maximum temperature
	Month	Day			
2016	July	18th to 20th	3	29.1 °C	31.6 °C
2017	June	17th to 21st	5	28.9 °C	30.2 °C
2018	June	25th to 27th	3	27.3 °C	27.5 °C
	July	5th to 9th	5	28.5 °C	29.6 °C
		22nd to 27th	6	29.1 °C	32.4 °C
	August	2nd to 7th	6	28.5 °C	29.8 °C
2019	July	23rd to 25th	3	32.6 °C	36.5 °C
	August	24th to 27th	4	30.5 °C	31.6 °C
2020	June	24th to 26th	3	29.3 °C	29.7 °C

4.2. Vegetation change with heatwaves

Here vegetation changes due to three heatwaves picked from table 1 will be analysed. The criteria for choosing those heatwaves are their high intensity and duration. These heatwave events are 5 days long heatwave in June/2017 with a maximum temperature of 30.2 °C, in July/2018 a heatwave event that lasted for 6 days with temperature spiking up to 32.4 °C, and the highly intense heatwave in the July of 2019 with the temperature reaching a maximum value of 36.5 °C.

Figure 2 Time series plot of NDVI from June to August for the year 2017

Figure 2 shows a sudden drop in NDVI after the heatwave struck in June/2017. The vegetation health kept fluctuating below 0.2 NDVI value until August.

Heatwave from 17th to 21st of June, 2017

Figure 3 Spatial maps of Milton Keynes before and after the heatwave in 2017

Figure 3 shows that the NDVI drop after the heatwave mostly happened in woodlands and grasslands. Crops even though are also affected at certain locations but their health has sprung back up mostly.

Figure 4 Time series plot of NDVI from June to August for the year 2018

During 2018, more than one heatwave event was noticed in July and one in August as well. So, the constant drop shown in Figure 4 during July that extended even to August is caused mostly by those events.

Heatwave from 22rd to 27th of July, 2018

Figure 5 Spatial maps of Milton Keynes before and after the heatwave in 2018

The year 2018 was particularly hot due to the recurring heatwaves and that effect can be seen on all vegetation types in figure 5. The crops and grasslands are showing signs of drought stress as well.

Figure 6 Time series plot of NDVI from June to August for the year 2019

NDVI plot for 2019 is better than 2018 because of less frequent droughts but the evidence of damage to vegetation health is still evident in figure 6. July and August are in vegetation stress due to two intense heatwaves.

Vegetation is under stress in both before and after maps of heatwaves because of a warm summer, but the heatwaves pushed them into further stress so much so that NDVI value is below zero at most points for crops and grasslands as evident from figure 7.

Heatwave from 23rd to 25th of July, 2019

Figure 7 Spatial maps of Milton Keynes before and after the heatwave in 2019

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6. Biographies

6.1. Ramla Khan

I am a PhD student currently working on analysing the relation between local tree species and the rising threat of heatwaves. In the past, I have worked in diverse fields ranging from road designing and machine learning to a number of natural disasters study at an artificial intelligence lab.

6.2. Kadmiel Maseyk

I am a plant eco-physiologist interested in how plant function affects ecosystem carbon and water biogeochemistry. I have a strong interest in plant and ecosystem responses to environmental variability and global change processes. My work is predominantly field based and has covered environments from the poles to the tropics.

6.3. Philip Wheeler

I am an ecologist and conservation biologist interested in a wide range of conservation and environmental management questions. My areas of teaching and research are quite varied, ranging from species ecology to wildlife monitoring and conservation, quantitative methods and spatial modelling.

6.4. Joseph Fennel

I am a scientist at The Open University interested in the intersection of data science and environmental biology. I like difficult challenges that need a mixture of high-performance computing, statistics and domain knowledge of plant/pest science.

6.5. Konstantin Stefanov

My work is focused on the design and evaluation of novel image sensors for scientific applications, manufactured in CMOS technology. Currently I am working on now are electron multiplication in CMOS imagers, achieving full depletion in CMOS sensors for maximum quantum efficiency, dynamic charge collection effects in CCDs, and radiation damage effects.